

Students' Perception of Idioms and Fixed Expressions: A Case of English-Majored Students at A University in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: This study, aims to investigate English-majored students' perceptions, usage, and challenges regarding idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing within a Vietnamese higher education context to identify gaps between students' awareness and their actual phraseological competence. Mixed-methods design was employed, integrating quantitative and qualitative data. A questionnaire with Likert-scale items was administered to examine students' perceptions, followed by semi-structured interviews with 40 participants to gain deeper insights into their experiences and difficulties. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were thematically coded. The findings indicate that although students generally recognize the importance of idioms and fixed expressions in enhancing cohesion and stylistic sophistication ($M = 3.67$), their actual use remains moderate ($M = 3.25$) and their confidence relatively low ($M = 2.67$). Students reported considerable difficulty in using these expressions appropriately ($M = 3.72$) and perceived insufficient instructional support from lecturers ($M = 2.65$). Qualitative findings further reveal that learners often rely on incidental exposure rather than systematic instruction, leading to avoidance or inappropriate usage. The study underscores the need for explicit, systematic instruction of idioms and fixed expressions within academic writing curricula. It recommends integrating corpus-informed pedagogy, guided practice, and AI-supported feedback to enhance students' phraseological competence and academic writing quality. This study contributes to the growing body of research on formulaic language by providing empirical evidence from the Vietnamese tertiary context. It highlights the critical role of phraseological competence in academic writing and offers pedagogical insights for bridging the gap between awareness and effective use.

KEYWORDS: idioms; fixed expressions; academic writing; EFL learners; phraseological competence; Vietnam

I. INTRODUCTION

Idioms, fixed expressions, and collocations, collectively referred to as formulaic sequences, are indispensable **components of the lexical repertoire in second language use**. Pawley and Syder (1983) described formulaic sequences as the key to "native-like selection" and "native-like fluency," while Wray (2002) demonstrated **argued that such sequences play a central role in the storage and retrieval of linguistic information**. In writing, idioms and fixed expressions serve multiple discourse functions, including providing conventionalized frames for organizing arguments, enhancing textual cohesion, and conveying stance or evaluation in ways that single words cannot (Howarth, 1998; Hyland, 2008). Jaén (2007), Skrzypek (2009), and Siyanova-Chanturia (2015) also confirmed that collocational competence is closely tied to fluency and accuracy in advanced L2 performance.

Despite this recognition, empirical studies show that learners of English, including advanced students, encounter substantial difficulties in using idioms and fixed expressions or related areas. Nesselhauf (2005) noted that collocational errors persist even among highly proficient learners, often resulting in unnatural or awkward sentences. Similarly, Peters (2015) reported that L2 students tend to underuse academic collocations while overusing informal combinations, which undermines the quality of their essays. Sonbul and Schmitt (2013) argued that this problem stems from insufficient exposure and limited instructional focus on phraseological units. In the Vietnamese context, such authors as Phan et al. (2022), My et al (2024) and Phuong et al. (2024) similarly found that English majors possessed only partial knowledge of collocations, with frequent transfer errors from Vietnamese.

As one of the four core language skills, writing is particularly sensitive to phraseological competence. Ariana (2010) emphasized that writing promotes critical thinking and language reflection, but students cannot express ideas logically and convincingly

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without mastery of collocations and idiomatic expressions. Studies of Vietnamese students' essays have consistently shown that collocational misuse and avoidance lead to texts that lack fluency, cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness (Vo & Nguyen, 2015; Tran & Nguyen, 2020). This aligns with international findings that academic writing requires not just grammar but also the ability to employ fixed expressions to guide readers, build arguments, and convey stance (Hyland, 2008; Chen & Baker, 2010).

The increasing pressures of globalization and the growing demand for international academic publication make the issue even more urgent. As Granger and Meunier (2008) pointed out, phraseology is a hallmark of advanced proficiency and a key criterion by which academic writing is evaluated. Without a solid command of idioms and fixed expressions, Vietnamese students risk producing essays that appear simplistic or inappropriate for academic contexts, lowering their competitiveness in local and global academic environments.

These challenges become especially apparent at Thu Dau Mot University, where English-majored students are expected to produce academic essays as part of their curriculum. Students may demonstrate adequate knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, yet their writing often lacks naturalness and cohesion because of inappropriate or insufficient use of idiomatic and fixed expressions. This gap affects their academic performance and hinders their long-term ability to participate in academic communication and professional discourse.

Given these challenges, an in-depth investigation into students' perception of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing is timely and necessary. Such a study will illuminate the extent of students' phraseological competence, identify recurring patterns of misuse, and explore the pedagogical interventions needed to improve instruction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Academic Essay Writing

Academic essay writing is a structured and formal mode of communication in higher education. According to Hyland (2008), it goes beyond language proficiency, requiring writers to adopt the conventions of their disciplinary community and present arguments logically, objectively, and with sufficient evidence. Similarly, Swales (1990) emphasized that academic writing operates within a "discourse community," in which writers must conform to the shared expectations, norms, and rhetorical practices of scholars in that field. Indeed, becoming expert academic writers involves developing an understanding and awareness of discipline-specific discourses, thereby linking linguistic form with communicative function in academic writing (Kaufhold, 2025).

Unlike general or everyday essay writing, which may prioritize personal expression, creativity, or narrative flow, academic essay writing is characterized by objectivity, critical engagement with sources, and formal tone (Bailey, 2018). It requires the writer to develop a thesis statement, construct coherent arguments, integrate citations from credible references, and adhere to recognized citation styles. In this sense, academic essay writing is a linguistic activity and an intellectual practice, where writers engage with existing knowledge, evaluate perspectives, and contribute new insights (Lea & Street, 1998).

Thus, academic essay writing is distinct from ordinary writing tasks: while the latter may tolerate subjectivity and colloquial language, the former demands analytical rigor, logical organization, and adherence to disciplinary conventions. It is a skill that allows students to participate in academic discourse, demonstrate critical thinking, and establish their credibility as members of a academic community (Hyland, 2008; Swales, 1990).

2.2. Idioms and Fixed Expressions

2.2.1. Idioms

The concept of idioms has been widely examined in linguistic studies and remains a central topic in phraseological research. Although definitions vary across theoretical traditions, most scholars agree that idioms are multi-word units characterized by semantic non-compositionality and structural fixedness. Palmer (1976) viewed idioms as groups of words whose collective meaning differs from the sum of their individual elements, emphasizing their deviation from literal interpretation. Building on this, Fernando (1996) described idioms as conventionalized and institutionalized expressions that are not fully analyzed and are deeply rooted in cultural and linguistic traditions.

Moon (1998) further expanded the definition by considering idioms as a subclass of fixed expressions that exhibit high frequency of occurrence, stability, and restricted modifiability. This perspective situates idioms within the larger framework of phraseological units, highlighting their systematic role in discourse. Similarly, Cowie, Mackin, and McCaig (1983) defined idioms as conventionalized word combinations whose meaning cannot be predicted from the meanings of the component words, stressing their pedagogical significance in foreign language learning.

From a more theoretical perspective, Nunberg, Sag, and Wasow (1994) argued that idioms should not be regarded as a homogeneous category but rather as expressions on a continuum of analyzability, from highly opaque to relatively transparent. Gläser (1988) also emphasized idioms' pragmatic and stylistic functions, noting that they serve not only as lexical items but also as markers of expressiveness, evaluation, and cohesion within discourse.

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2.2.2. Fixed Expressions

The notion of fixed expressions has occupied a central position in the study of phraseology, particularly concerning the broader concept of formulaic language. Fixed expressions are generally understood as conventionalized multi-word units that occur with high frequency and are stored and retrieved as wholes rather than newly generated each time in discourse. According to Cowie, Mackin, and McCaig (1983), fixed expressions are institutionalized word combinations whose meanings and functions are widely recognized by the speech community. Their definition emphasizes conventionality and restricted variability, distinguishing them from free word combinations.

Gläser (1988) reinforced this view by arguing that fixed expressions are characterized by stability, recurrent use, and high lexical cohesion. They are “fixed” not in the sense of being entirely immutable, but because their form and meaning have become standardized through usage, making them predictable to members of a linguistic community.

From a corpus-based perspective, Moon (1998) defined fixed expressions as prefabricated units that display varying degrees of fixedness and idiomaticity, ranging from transparent formulas, in other words, to semi-transparent or opaque sequences. Moon's work situated fixed expressions within a continuum of phraseological units, highlighting their central role in spoken and written registers.

More recently, Wray (2002) conceptualized fixed expressions as part of the broader category of formulaic sequences, describing them as multi-word strings stored and processed holistically by speakers. This psycholinguistic approach explains why fixed expressions contribute to fluency and why learners often struggle when absent from their linguistic repertoire.

2.3. Roles of Idioms and Fixed Expressions in Academic Essay Writing

Using idioms and fixed expressions has been recognized as an essential component of phraseological competence, significantly shaping academic writing quality. While both forms contribute to fluency and naturalness, their functions and appropriateness in formal writing differ. Idioms and metaphorical language are a natural part of academic discourse, serving many functions such as organizing arguments, clarifying abstract meanings, creating coherence, and expressing the academic voice of the writer (Simpson & Mendis, 2003; Miller, 2020; Wang et al., 2024). In the context of English-majored students, understanding how idioms and fixed expressions operate is essential for improving coherence, stance expression, and overall persuasiveness in academic essays.

Contribution to Coherence and Cohesion

Coherence and cohesion are widely regarded as the foundation of effective academic writing. Halliday and Hasan (1976) emphasized that cohesion arises from using lexical and grammatical devices that tie texts together.

Fixed expressions, particularly lexical bundles and discourse markers, are pivotal in this process. As Hyland (2008) observed, expressions such as *on the other hand*, *in conclusion*, or *it should be noted that* provide readers with clear signals that guide them through the writer's reasoning. These sequences create textual flow, reduce ambiguity, and enhance readability.

Idioms, in contrast, contribute less directly to cohesion but can still enrich textual coherence when used judiciously. For example, idiomatic phrases may function as stylistic devices highlighting contrast or evaluation, making transitions more engaging (Fernando, 1996). However, idioms are less frequent in academic registers because their figurative and culture-bound meanings may disrupt clarity. Thus, while fixed expressions ensure structural cohesion, idioms can provide stylistic coherence by reinforcing evaluative or rhetorical points when appropriately selected.

Role in Expressing Stance, Evaluation, and Persuasion

Another critical function of idioms and fixed expressions is expressing stance and evaluation. According to Hyland (2005), stance markers allow writers to project authority, hedge claims, and guide readers' interpretations. Fixed expressions such as *it is evident that* or *no doubt are* particularly effective in signaling conviction. At the same time, formulas like *it seems that* or *it may be argued that* serve hedging functions. These conventionalized patterns are central to academic persuasion, helping writers balance assertiveness with caution.

Idioms, however, can also function as evaluative tools, though they must be used cautiously. Cowie, Mackin, and McCaig (1983) argued that idioms encapsulate cultural imagery and rhetorical resonance, allowing writers to convey attitude or evaluation indirectly. For example, idiomatic metaphors strengthen argumentation by embedding vivid language that resonates with readers. However, as Biber et al. (1999) noted, idioms are relatively rare in academic registers because of their informal tone and cultural specificity. Overuse of idioms may undermine the objectivity required in academic discourse. Consequently, fixed expressions are central to stance in academic writing, while idioms serve as supplementary rhetorical devices that can enhance persuasiveness when used strategically.

2.4. Common Difficulties Faced by EFL Learners

Despite their significance, both idioms and fixed expressions pose considerable challenges for EFL learners. Pawley and Snyder (1983) pointed out that native-like fluency depends on the mastery of prefabricated chunks, yet learners often lack sufficient exposure to these units.

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In the context of English as a foreign language, the use of idioms in academic writing poses many challenges for learners. Studies show that the main difficulties stem from the ambiguity of meaning and the degree of fixity of idioms, making it difficult for learners to infer meaning and apply them accurately in an academic context (Peters, 2016; Soto-Sierra & Ferreira, 2024; Szudarski, 2017; Zhao, 2024). For idioms, the primary difficulty lies in semantic opacity and cultural specificity. As Wray (2002) explained, idioms must be learned holistically and in authentic contexts, which makes them difficult to acquire in traditional classroom settings. Students may avoid idioms entirely or misuse them, leading to awkward or unclear writing.

Fixed expressions, though more transparent, also create difficulties. Howarth (1998) observed that learners frequently overuse a limited repertoire of formulas, resulting in repetitive or mechanical writing. Chen and Baker (2010) further demonstrated that non-native writers tend to rely on fewer and less varied lexical bundles than native speakers, which limits the sophistication of their texts. For Vietnamese students, the exam-oriented curriculum often emphasizes grammar and vocabulary in isolation, leaving less room for phraseological competence. This gap results in grammatically accurate essays that lack cohesion, rhetorical nuance, and natural flow.

Overall, idioms and fixed expressions contribute to the quality of academic essay writing, but in distinct ways. Fixed expressions are indispensable for coherence, cohesion, and stance expression, while idioms add rhetorical depth and stylistic resonance when used sparingly and appropriately. The main challenge for EFL learners, especially in Vietnam, is acquiring sufficient phraseological competence to balance accuracy, fluency, and appropriateness in academic writing. Addressing these challenges requires explicit instruction, corpus-informed pedagogy, and opportunities to practice idioms and fixed expressions in authentic academic contexts.

Within the broad category of multi-word vocabulary units, idioms, fixed expressions, and lexical bundles represent related but distinct phenomena. Idioms are characterized by non-literal meaning and are often stylistically informal, which limits their appropriateness in academic discourse. Fixed expressions, on the other hand, are conventionalized phrases that provide cohesion, stance, and rhetorical clarity, while lexical bundles are recurrent sequences identified by frequency in corpora that serve important discourse functions in academic texts (Hyland, 2008; Wray, 2002). In the present study, the analytical focus is placed on how these units, particularly idioms and fixed expressions, are employed in students' academic essay writing. This focus allows the research to capture both the challenges of non-literal language and the critical role of formulaic sequences in achieving cohesion and naturalness in academic discourse.

2.5. Errors regarding idioms and fixed expressions

Idioms and fixed expressions constitute an essential part of English phraseology, conveying meanings that go beyond the sum of their individual words. Their figurative nature, restricted variability, and contextual sensitivity often make them a challenging aspect of English language mastery for EFL learners. As a result, numerous studies have investigated learners' difficulties and types of errors in idiom use across different contexts. For instance, Alkarazoun (2015) examined structural and semantic errors among Jordanian undergraduates; Lennon (1991) discussed error identification and classification in idiomatic usage; Fernando and Flavell (1981) explored the fixedness and semantic opacity of idioms; and Liu (2008) provided a comprehensive account of idiom comprehension, acquisition, and pragmatic constraints. More recent works such as Ababneh (2017), Boers and Lindstromberg (2008), and Rizq (2015) have further highlighted the persistent challenges EFL learners face, including form-based distortions, literal interpretations, and inappropriate pragmatic choices in academic or formal writing.

These researchers have outlined a wide range of error types, spanning morphological, semantic, pragmatic, and interlingual dimensions, reflecting the complex nature of idiomatic competence. Building upon this body of research, the present study focuses specifically on **three major categories of idiomatic errors** most relevant to written discourse in the Vietnamese EFL context: **form-based errors, meaning-based errors, and pragmatic errors**. This tripartite classification provides a focused analytical framework for identifying, interpreting, and discussing idiom-related inaccuracies in students' academic essays.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

With the objective of investigating the use of idioms and fixed expressions among English-majored students at Thu Dau Mot University, this study will employ a mixed-methods design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to investigate the use of idioms and fixed expressions among English-majored students at Thu Dau Mot University. A mixed-methods approach is a combination and integration of qualitative and quantitative methods in the same study. This approach is particularly suitable for studies in the fields of education, health science, psychology and sociology (Denscombe, 2008). The main purpose of the mixed research method specifically is that the use of a combination of quantitative and qualitative research provides a better understanding of the definitely complex aspects of the research than the approach: single approach (Creswell & Clark, 2007). Greene, Caracelli, and Graham (1989) pointed out that the outstanding advantages of mixed research methods are methods that

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help researchers compare and contrast research results obtained from the method. The integration of both data types will strengthen the validity and reliability of the research findings (Johnson & Christensen, 2014).

Questionnaire

A questionnaire was administered to participants prior to the interviews. The questionnaire included Likert-scale items to capture students' nuanced perceptions of idioms and fixed expressions in their academic writing (Table 1).

Table 1. Questionnaire items investigating students' perceptions of idioms and fixed expressions in their academic writing

No	Factors	Statements
1	Perceived importance	I think idioms and fixed expressions are important in academic essay writing.
2	Perceived level of use	I often use idioms and fixed expressions in my academic essays.
3	Perceived confidence	I feel confident when using idioms and fixed expressions in academic writing.
4	Perception of teachers' guidance	My lecturers provide sufficient guidance on how to use idioms and fixed expressions in academic essays.
5	Perceived difficulty	I find it difficult to use idioms and fixed expressions appropriately in academic essay writing.

The use of this instrument contributes to reinforcing the validity of the study's findings and enabling multidimensional insight into students' perceptions and abilities.

Interviews

Semi-structured interviews in English were conducted with a selected group of students to provide qualitative insights. This method allows for flexibility while still maintaining focus on research objectives (Creswell, 2012). The interviews aimed to uncover participants' perspectives on the roles of idioms and fixed expressions in academic writing, their perceived difficulties, and their strategies for improvement. Following ethical guidelines, interviews were recorded with participants' consent, transcribed, and coded for thematic analysis (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). As several participants who join the interview had their own personal concerns and specific scheduling difficulties, they will be each questioned separately at a time that was convenient for them.

3.2. Setting and participants of the study

The setting

The current study was conducted at Thu Dau Mot University, where the English Language program emphasizes developing academic writing skills as an essential curriculum component. Academic writing is considered a key skill for English-majored students, since it equips them to engage in academic communication, critical thinking, and professional development. The inclusion of idioms and fixed expressions in the programme enrich students' writing, improving cohesion, precision, and stylistic naturalness.

Participants and the sampling of the study

The student participants who are current English-majored students at Thu Dau Mot University were chosen to represent a homogeneous group regarding age, learning background, and exposure to academic writing tasks. All participants had studied English for at least eight years and had already completed foundational grammar, vocabulary, and paragraph writing courses before taking essay writing classes. The focus on second-year students will be justified because they had already gained initial exposure to academic essay writing. However, they faced significant challenges applying idioms and fixed expressions effectively.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 40 student participants who had submitted their papers at Thu Dau Mot University. The sampling approach employed a random selection procedure to ensure objectivity and to reflect the diverse academic backgrounds and teaching experiences of the participants.

3.3. Data collection and analysis procedures

Questionnaire procedures

Prior to administering the questionnaire, the research purposes were clearly described to the students. The questionnaire papers were collected as soon as they are completed. Descriptive statistics, including means (M) and standard deviations (SD), were computed to examine students' perceptions of idioms and fixed expression in academic writing.

Interview procedures

Forty students (aged 20-22) were randomly selected for interviews. Each participant was interviewed individually at a convenient time. Semi-structured questions focused on students' goals in learning idioms and fixed expressions, their perceived roles in essay writing, common challenges, and strategies for improvement. Interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and coded

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thematically. Thematic analysis followed Kumar (2011), ensuring that findings were systematically organized and aligned with research objectives.

Data analysis

While quantitative data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, normalized frequency), qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis, with codes developed inductively and refined iteratively.

3.4. Ethical considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with standard ethical guidelines for educational research. Participation was voluntary, and all participants provided informed consent prior to the study. Confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing participants' names and assigning codes for data analysis. Students were informed that their performance data would be used solely for research purposes and would not impact on their grades. Hopefully, this study serves as one of the academic product of the scientific research project coded DT.26.2-563 conducted at Thu Dau Mot University.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

4.1.1. Results from the questionnaire

Table 2. Results from the questionnaire

No	Factor	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Perceived importance	I think idioms and fixed expressions are important in academic essay writing.	3.67	0.968
2	Perceived level of use	I often use idioms and fixed expressions in my academic essays.	3.25	0.967
3	Perceived confidence	I feel confident when using idioms and fixed expressions in academic writing.	2.67	0.879
4	Perception of teachers' guidance	My lecturers provide sufficient guidance on how to use idioms and fixed expressions in academic essays.	2.65	0.976
5	Perceived difficulty	I find it difficult to use idioms and fixed expressions appropriately in academic essay writing.	3.72	0.987

Based on the questionnaire results displayed on Table 2, the descriptive statistics reveal several noteworthy patterns regarding students' perceptions and use of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing. Overall, the findings indicate that while students demonstrate a certain level of awareness of the importance of these linguistic features, their actual use and confidence in employing them remain relatively limited.

First, the factor of **perceived importance** obtained a mean score of $M = 3.67$ ($SD = 0.968$), suggesting that students generally acknowledge the role of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing. This relatively high mean indicates that most respondents agree that these expressions can contribute to more natural and sophisticated writing. However, awareness of importance does not necessarily translate into frequent or effective use in practice.

In fact, the mean score for **perceived level of use** is lower ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 0.967$), indicating that students only occasionally incorporate idioms and fixed expressions into their academic essays. This moderate level of use suggests that although students recognize their value, they may not feel sufficiently prepared to apply them consistently in their writing.

More importantly, the data reveal a relatively low level of **confidence** among students when using such expressions ($M = 2.67$, $SD = 0.879$). This result implies that many students feel uncertain about whether they are using idioms and fixed expressions appropriately in academic contexts. A similar trend is observed in students' **perception of teachers' guidance**, which received a mean score of $M = 2.65$ ($SD = 0.976$). This finding suggests that students may perceive limited instructional support or explicit guidance on how to effectively integrate idiomatic or formulaic language into academic writing.

Furthermore, the highest mean score is found in **perceived difficulty** ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.987$), indicating that students generally find it challenging to use idioms and fixed expressions appropriately in academic essays. This perception of difficulty may partly explain the relatively low level of use and confidence reported by the respondents.

Taken together, these findings suggest that although students are aware of the importance of idioms and fixed expressions, their practical use and confidence remain limited. The results highlight the need for more explicit instruction and pedagogical support to help students develop greater competence in employing formulaic language in academic writing.

4.1.2. Results from the interviews

The purpose of the interviews was to explore students' understanding, attitudes, and challenges when using idiomatic and fixed expressions in their writing. Specifically, the interviews aimed to identify students' goals in learning English, their awareness of idioms and fixed expressions, and their views on the importance of these linguistic elements in enhancing the quality of their

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writing. Additionally, the interviews examined how idioms and fixed expressions are introduced and practiced in classroom instruction, how frequently students incorporate them into their essays, and their level of confidence in using them appropriately. Seven major open-ended questions were developed to gain a deeper understanding of students' perceptions and experiences regarding the use of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing, as follows: 1) *What are your main goals in learning English, particularly in relation to academic writing?* 2) *How do you perceive the role of idioms and fixed expressions in learning English?* 3) *How did you first learn about idioms and fixed expressions, and in what contexts have you encountered them?* 4) *What are your perceptions of the role of idioms and fixed expressions in improving academic essay writing?* 5) *Can you describe the difficulties you face when using idioms and fixed expressions in your essays?* 6) *How confident are you in applying idioms and fixed expressions appropriately in your academic writing?* 7) *When learning idioms or fixed expressions, what aspects do you pay most attention to (e.g., meaning, usage, context)?*

The interviews were recorded and re-listened, to enter the data into Microsoft Excel, and compare and contrast the participants' remarks. The study's goal was to organize interview data after the transcription services. Several representative excerpts from the interview responses are summarized in Table 10.

The interviews revealed a range of perspectives regarding students' understanding, attitudes, and challenges in using idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing. Analysis of the responses indicated several prominent themes related to students' goals, perceptions, learning sources, challenges, and confidence levels.

A dominant theme across the interviews was students' aspiration to achieve academic fluency and professional competence in writing. Many participants expressed that mastering idioms and fixed expressions was an essential component of developing academic writing skills and demonstrating advanced English proficiency. For instance, Student 2 emphasized an academic goal linked to higher-level study, stating, *"I aim to strengthen my academic writing for postgraduate studies,"* and added that *"Idioms and fixed expressions enhance clarity and cohesion."* Similarly, Student 5 highlighted research-oriented writing, noting, *"I want to improve my academic writing for research papers,"* and explaining that *"Idioms and fixed expressions show a good command of English."* This pattern also appeared in other responses: Student 4 connected idiomatic language with proficiency *"Idioms and fixed expressions play a crucial role in writing because they show language proficiency,"* Student 30 framed them as evidence of mastery *"Idioms and fixed expressions reflect language mastery."* Collectively, these comments reveal students' strong motivation to use idiomatic language as a means of attaining academic success and linguistic sophistication.

Another prominent theme was the recognition of idioms and fixed expressions as valuable tools for enhancing writing fluency, coherence, and overall quality. Many students agreed that such expressions make their writing more natural and refined. Another prominent theme was the recognition of idioms and fixed expressions as valuable tools for enhancing writing fluency, coherence, and overall quality. Many students agreed that such expressions make their writing more natural and refined. Student 1 observed, *"Idioms and fixed expressions make my writing sound more polished,"* suggesting that students perceive idioms and fixed expressions as contributing to a more sophisticated academic voice. Similar views were expressed by Student 2, who noted that these expressions *"Idioms and fixed expressions enhance clarity and cohesion,"* and Student 9, who stated they *"Idioms and fixed expressions add fluency and coherence."* In the same vein, Student 10 emphasized their importance *"Idioms and fixed expressions are important for fluency,"* and explained that they can make essays *"more academic,"* while Student 13 *"Idioms and fixed expressions are valuable for enhancing coherence."* Student 15 highlighted their role in helping to *"Idioms and fixed expressions help link ideas smoothly."* Several others reinforced this perceived quality-improving function, such as Student 21 *"Idioms and fixed expressions help link ideas,"* and Student 29 *"Idioms and fixed expressions help with transitions."* These perspectives collectively demonstrate that students understand idiomatic competence as a key indicator of advanced language mastery.

Students also described various sources from which they learned idioms and fixed expressions. Most participants mentioned classroom instruction, reading materials, and exposure through media such as films or online resources. Student 4 shared, *"I first learned them from lecturers and English TV shows,"* while Student 8 noted, *"I learned them through reading and lecturer explanations."* Media exposure was also common, as Student 17 explained, *"I first encountered them through movies,"* and Student 1 similarly reported learning them *"I first learned them through reading and movies."* In addition, several participants highlighted the role of digital learning, with Student 3 mentioning *"I first encountered them in English textbooks and online resources."* Student 12 referring to *"I learned them through online lessons and reading,"* and Student 36 stating, *"I learned idioms and fixed expressions through online platforms."* Overall, these responses indicate that although idioms and fixed expressions are introduced in formal instruction, students' development of idiomatic competence is largely shaped by self-directed exposure through reading, media, and online materials, often occurring incidentally rather than through systematic, structured guidance.

A recurring challenge identified by many participants was the difficulty in distinguishing between formal and informal idioms. Students expressed uncertainty about which expressions are appropriate for academic contexts. Student 1 noted that idioms and fixed expressions are *"tricky to use in formal contexts,"* and Student 2 mentioned that they *"sometimes forget their exact forms,"*

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while Student 3 admitted, *"I often confuse informal idioms with formal phrases,"* including Student 6, who found it *"challenging to apply them appropriately,"* and Student 9, who stated, *"I struggle to apply them naturally."* and Student 10 added, *"I fear using informal idioms."* Similar concerns were also reflected by Student 12 who stated that some expressions *"...but sometimes they sound informal..."*, Student 16 similarly said, *"I often forget them."* Student 22, who said, *"I worry about formality,"* and Student 28, who described idioms as *"They are useful but risky in formal writing."* These findings reveal that students encounter both linguistic and pragmatic difficulties, including issues with structural accuracy and situational appropriateness.

Another key theme emerging from the interviews was students' limited confidence in using idioms and fixed expressions effectively. Many participants reported only moderate confidence, citing uncertainty about meaning, form, and context. Student 1 reflected, *"I focus on meaning and appropriateness, but still feel only moderately confident about using them correctly."* Similarly, Student 3 stated, *"My confidence is low,"* and Student 4 admitted, *"I'm not very confident yet."* This limited confidence was also evident in Student 9, who said, *"My confidence is limited,"* and Student 16, who likewise reported, *"My confidence is low."* Even when students expressed higher confidence, it was often conditional or partial: Student 6 explained, *"I'm fairly confident when I check their meanings first,"* while Student 8 noted, *"I'm confident using fixed expressions, but less with idioms."* These statements highlight a need for greater practice and lecturer feedback to strengthen learners' confidence and precision.

Finally, most students reported focusing primarily on meaning, usage, and context when learning idioms rather than on grammatical or structural accuracy. This meaning-and-context orientation was also clear in Student 1, who stated, *"I focus on meaning and appropriateness,"* and Student 2 similarly noted, *"I focus mainly on context and collocational accuracy."* Student 7 said, *"I pay attention mainly to meaning and usage,"* while Student 10, who explained, *"I focus on context and proper usage."* In the same vein, Student 16: *"I focus on correct form and meaning"* and Student 21: *"I focus on meaning and grammar,"* Student 32 reported, *"I focus on context and formal usage,"* and Student 39 added, *"I focus on usage and context,"*, the overall pattern indicates that learners tend to prioritize semantic understanding and contextual appropriateness over structural precision. This focus on semantics over form suggests that learners prioritize understanding over correctness, which may contribute to form-based or collocational errors observed in their writing.

The interviews revealed that students view idioms and fixed expressions as valuable tools for enhancing academic writing, fluency, and expression. Most participants learned them through lecturers, reading, and media, recognizing their role in improving coherence, vocabulary richness, and stylistic sophistication. However, many struggled to distinguish between formal and informal idioms and recall the correct forms, resulting in moderate confidence levels. Students emphasized the importance of meaning, usage, and contextual appropriateness when learning and applying these expressions. While idioms were seen as helpful in demonstrating linguistic competence and cultural understanding, learners remained cautious about their academic suitability. In sum, idioms and fixed expressions are perceived as both challenging and beneficial, offering potential to elevate writing quality when applied thoughtfully within appropriate academic contexts.

4.2. DISCUSSION

The qualitative interviews with thirty English-majored students revealed a mixture of **awareness, aspiration, and difficulty** regarding the use of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing. These findings are quite in line with those obtained from the questionnaire. The majority acknowledged their importance in enhancing fluency and coherence but admitted confusion about formal appropriateness. **Student 3** emphasized the same uncertainty about register, noting, *"I often confuse informal idioms with formal phrases."* Likewise, **Student 10** expressed this concern clearly, stating, *"They make my essays more academic, but I fear using informal idioms."* These comments reflect students' partial understanding of idiomatic usage and their concern with violating academic norms, reinforcing **Hyland's (2008)** view that idiomatic competence is an indicator of rhetorical maturity. Previous studies have also shown that idioms and metaphorical language are a natural part of academic discourse, serving many functions such as organizing arguments, clarifying abstract meanings, creating coherence, and expressing the academic voice of the writer (Simpson & Mendis, 2003; Miller, 2020; Wang et al., 2024)

Many students also reported prioritizing meaning over structure, which corresponds with the quantitative dominance of meaning-based and pragmatic errors. **Student 7** explicitly stated, *"I pay attention mainly to meaning and usage,"* indicating that semantic understanding is often foregrounded more than formal accuracy. In addition, several students described learning idioms through informal exposure rather than systematic instruction; for example, **Student 17** noted, *"I first encountered them through movies,"* suggesting that exposure is incidental rather than systematic, a limitation that Wray (2002) described as typical when formulaic language is acquired implicitly rather than through guided awareness.

The findings and theoretical considerations of this project indicate a clear need to strengthen both students' and lecturers' awareness of the role of idioms and fixed expressions in academic essay writing. Rather than being viewed as optional or purely stylistic elements, idioms and fixed expressions constitute an essential component of phraseological competence that supports coherence, fluency, and rhetorical effectiveness in academic discourse.

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For students, limited awareness of idioms and fixed expressions often leads to two opposing tendencies: complete avoidance or inappropriate use in academic essays. This situation suggests the importance of explicit pedagogical intervention. Instruction should emphasize the functional distinction between idioms and fixed expressions, highlighting that while idioms require careful and selective use, fixed expressions are central to structuring arguments, signaling logical relationships, and expressing authorial stance in academic writing. Learning activities such as guided analysis of authentic academic texts can help students recognize how these expressions operate in context and how they contribute to textual cohesion and disciplinary conventions. Encouraging students to compare fixed expressions with more explicit paraphrases may further enhance their sensitivity to register and apply appropriately.

Interview findings revealed that students valued idioms and fixed expressions for enhancing fluency, coherence, and stylistic sophistication. However, they expressed moderate confidence and uncertainty about their proper use. Most participants reported that idioms were occasionally mentioned in class but rarely practiced systematically. Although students possess a general awareness of the importance of idioms and fixed expressions, their actual competence remains limited due to insufficient instruction and exposure.

By bridging traditional pedagogy with digital innovation, students can develop not only accuracy but also stylistic authenticity, intercultural awareness, and communicative confidence in their English writing. The study demonstrates that improving idiomatic competence requires a multi-layered strategy: learner autonomy supported by AI tools, lecturer-led scaffolding and error analysis, curriculum-level integration of formulaic language, and institutional investment in technological infrastructure. Taken together, these recommendations highlight the powerful synergy between applied linguistics and artificial intelligence in helping learners move beyond literal translation to more natural, context-appropriate, and effective use of idioms and fixed expressions in English writing.

The practical implications of this study emphasize the urgent need to integrate idioms and fixed expressions into academic writing curricula rather than treating them as isolated elements within speaking or vocabulary lessons. Pedagogically, the study highlights the importance of integrating idiomatic competence into academic writing curricula. It underscores that idioms and fixed expressions are not merely stylistic embellishments but essential components of discourse coherence and lexical sophistication. Theoretically, the study extends existing research on formulaic language by applying idiomatic analysis within the Vietnamese tertiary context. It reinforces prior arguments by Wray (2002) and Hyland (2008) that idiomatic knowledge contributes to fluency, cohesion, and pragmatic appropriateness. Practically, the research provides concrete recommendations for curriculum developers, suggesting institutional strategies such as creating idiomatic databases, organizing professional development workshops, and integrating AI-enhanced feedback systems. These contributions have the potential to improve teaching effectiveness and students' academic writing performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study investigated the use of idioms and fixed expressions by English-majored students in academic essay writing, employing both document analysis and semi-structured interviews. The quantitative findings revealed that although students are aware of the importance of idioms and fixed expressions, they demonstrated a moderate level of idiomatic proficiency, with substantial variation among individuals. Based on the results of the current study and the related literature, several pedagogical and strategic recommendations are proposed for both teachers and students to enhance the use of idioms and fixed expressions in academic writing.

Note: This study serves as one of the academic product of the scientific research project coded DT.26.2-563 conducted at Thu Dau Mot University.

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